

Review

A Comprehensive Look at Low Back Pain: A Dual Perspective from Western and Traditional Chinese Medicine (Part 2).

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Abstract

Low back pain is a major cause of global disability, imposing a significant burden on individuals and healthcare systems. While conventional approaches offer relief, the growing interest in complementary therapies demands a rigorous evaluation of other options. Traditional Chinese Medicine offers a holistic perspective, treating low back pain as a symptom of imbalances in *Qi* and *Xue*. The objective of this work was to analyse the scientific evidence available on the effectiveness of the main tools of Traditional Chinese Medicine in the treatment of low back pain. To do this, a literature review was carried out in electronic databases (PubMed and SciELO) to identify systematic reviews with meta-analyses published between 2020 and 2025 that addressed the use of Traditional Chinese Medicine for low back pain. Ten studies were included that evaluated the effectiveness of various Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques. Acupuncture was shown to be effective in reducing pain and improving function, with promising results for both acute and chronic low back pain. *Tui Na*, wet cupping, and *Gua Sha* revealed significant effects in decreasing pain and improving physical function, with a favourable safety profile. Movement therapies, such as *Qigong* and Tai Chi, showed benefits in function and quality of life. However, the studies presented methodological limitations, such as high heterogeneity and moderate-to-low evidence quality, which require caution in interpreting the results. Thus, the techniques of Traditional Chinese Medicine, namely acupuncture, *Tui Na*, cupping therapy, *Gua Sha*, *Qigong*, and Tai Chi, present promising evidence of effectiveness in the treatment of low back pain. The findings suggest that these approaches can be a valuable complement to conventional treatments.

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1. Introduction

Low back pain is a major cause of global disability, imposing a significant burden on individuals and healthcare systems¹⁻⁴. While conventional approaches offer relief, the growing interest in complementary therapies demands a rigorous evaluation of other options. Traditional Chinese Medicine offers a holistic perspective, treating low back pain as a symptom of imbalances in *Qi* and *Xue*⁵⁻⁸. In a previous paper⁹ we explored the Western Medicine perspective on low back pain, namely the anatomy and structure of the lumbar spine, the various types of low back pain, its causes, diagnosis, and common conventional treatments, also introducing the Traditional Chinese Medicine view. Building on the provided framework, this study aims to explore the available scientific evidence about

the effect of the various Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques on low back pain, focusing on recent meta-analytic studies.

2. Methodology

This study was prepared as a literature review with the objective of analysing the effectiveness of Traditional Chinese Medicine in the treatment of low back pain. The bibliographic research was carried out in the electronic databases PubMed and SciELO, covering a period of 5 years (from 2020 to 2025). The search strategy included the use of indexing terms (descriptors) in English, combined with each other to optimise the results. The descriptors used were: "Traditional Chinese Medicine", "Acupuncture", "Tui Na", "Cupping", "Chinese Herbal Medicine", "Qigong", "Taichi", "Low Back Pain". The selection of articles focused on systematic reviews with meta-analysis, as they are studies with high scientific evidence, capable of synthesising the results of multiple primary investigations. Articles that addressed the application of one or more Traditional Chinese Medicine modalities in the treatment of low back pain were included, evaluating outcomes such as pain reduction, improvement in physical function, and patients' quality of life. Any experimental studies, expert opinions, systematic reviews, and other articles that did not fit the defined time and publication type criteria were excluded from the analysis.

3. Results

According to the research carried out in the indicated databases, 10 systematic review studies with meta-analysis were included. Of these, 5 concern the application of acupuncture¹⁰⁻¹⁴ (including 1 on pharmacopuncture¹²), 1 analyses the application of *Tui Na*¹⁵, 2 on cupping intervention^{14,16}, 1 on *Gua Sha*¹⁷, 1 on *Qigong*¹⁸, and 1 on Taichi¹⁹.

3.1. Acupuncture

Acupuncture is defined by the insertion of small needles into certain points on the body²⁰. The action on these points has the ability to regulate the various human biological systems²¹.

Acupuncture is considered a complementary therapy frequently used for pain²², and is therefore systematically used for the relief of low back pain^{23,24}.

The study by Su *et al.*¹⁰ evaluated the effectiveness of acupuncture in the treatment of acute low back pain. The research, which included 13 randomised clinical trials with 707 patients, focused on three main aspects: pain intensity, functional status, and use of analgesics. For pain intensity, the results of this study showed that acupuncture has a statistically significant association with pain improvement. Patients who received acupuncture had a reduction in the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) score of -1.75. Regarding functionality, the study presented mixed results. Acupuncture did not have a significant impact on the Roland-Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ) but showed a significant improvement in the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI), with a reduction of -12.84. For the use of analgesics, acupuncture was associated with a significant reduction in the number of analgesics taken by patients, with a mean difference of -3.19 tablets. Thus, the study suggests that acupuncture may be effective in improving pain intensity and reducing the use of analgesics in patients with acute low back pain. However, the results regarding the improvement of physical function were not entirely consistent.

In the case of the study by Sun *et al.*¹¹, it aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of non-pharmacological Chinese therapies in the treatment of degenerative lumbar spinal stenosis. 37 studies with a total of 2965 participants were analysed. The results showed that acupuncture, applied for 6 to 8 weeks, was significantly superior to sham acupuncture in reducing low back pain in the medium term (6 months) and in improving lumbar spine function. In the short term, the available evidence suggested that acupuncture can be effective in reducing low back pain and improving function in the short term (3 months), but it did not have a significant impact on the pain that radiated to the lower limbs. In addition, acupuncture is effective for improving disability and walking ability compared

to sham acupuncture. Therefore, the study suggests that acupuncture presents favourable results compared to simulated acupuncture for patients with lumbar spinal stenosis. The results are positive in reducing low back pain in the short and medium term, in improving lumbar function, disability, and walking ability.

Another study¹⁴ sought to study the effectiveness and safety of Traditional Chinese Medicine in the treatment of low back and neck pain. This study analysed 57 randomised clinical trials, comparing Traditional Chinese Medicine with Western medicine. The analysis showed that Traditional Chinese Medicine was superior to Western medicine in the clinical improvement of pain. A sensitivity analysis later confirmed that Traditional Chinese Medicine has better results in the treatment of low back pain than Western medicine. Similarly, the study indicated that Traditional Chinese Medicine may have a superior analgesic effect to that of Western medicine, although the authors state that this conclusion is based on limited evidence. With regard to safety, Traditional Chinese Medicine presented a favourable safety profile, with 20 studies reporting the absence of serious side effects. Considering these results, this study suggests that Traditional Chinese Medicine can achieve better clinical effectiveness and analgesic effects when compared to Western medicine in the treatment of low back and neck pain, also highlighting a favourable safety profile. It is important to mention that the authors state that the techniques analysed included acupuncture, acupressure, and cupping therapy.

In turn, the study by Byun *et al.*¹² evaluated the effectiveness of pharmacoacupuncture (or phytoacupuncture) in the treatment of patients with lumbar intervertebral disc herniation. Pharmacoacupuncture is the injection of liquid herbal extracts into acupuncture points. This study analysed 16 randomised clinical trials, with 1507 participants. The results showed that pharmacoacupuncture can produce a significant improvement in pain intensity, measured by VAS, compared to the control groups. This improvement was observed both in treatments with less than 14 days and in those of longer duration. It also demonstrated a positive effect on the functional recovery of patients, evaluated by disability questionnaires (JOA and ODI). Only two of the 16 studies included reported adverse events, such as local pain at the injection site, nausea, and skin rashes. No serious adverse events were reported. Interestingly, the authors observed that pharmacoacupuncture, when used in conjunction with other therapies, showed a superior effect than pharmacoacupuncture alone, suggesting that a multimodal approach may be more effective. In line with these results, the authors concluded that this particular approach has a positive effect on pain relief and functional recovery in patients with lumbar intervertebral disc herniation, without the occurrence of serious adverse events.

Finally, the study by Zhang *et al.*¹³ evaluated the effectiveness of different acupuncture methods for non-specific chronic low back pain. The study included 27 randomised clinical trials, with 2579 patients, and compared the various approaches to determine the most effective. The analysis showed that the three most effective treatments for non-specific chronic low back pain were acupuncture with heated needles (by moxa), intensive therapy with silver needles, and treatment based on the theory of the sinew channels. For specific pain relief, the three treatments that stood out were electroacupuncture + heated needles, intensive therapy with silver needles, and acupuncture with heated needles. Furthermore, for the improvement of mobility, the study identified treatment based on the theory of the sinew channels, conventional acupuncture, and electroacupuncture as the best options. The study then recommends acupuncture with heated needles, electroacupuncture with heated needles, and treatment based on the sinew channel theory for patients with non-specific chronic low back pain. If the goal is pain relief, electroacupuncture is the most suggested approach. On the other hand, for patients with reduced mobility, treatment based on the sinew channel theory is the most recommended.

3.2. *Tui Na*, Cupping, and *Guasha*

Tui Na, in other words, traditional Chinese massage, is an ancient technique mentioned in several medical classics, such as the *Huangdi Neijing*²⁵. This massage uses various manipulative techniques on soft tissues and chiropractic adjustments²⁶.

A study developed by Yang *et al.*¹⁵ evaluated the effectiveness and safety of *Tui Na* in the treatment of non-specific chronic low back pain. 15 randomised clinical trials were included, with a total of 1390 patients. *Tui Na* demonstrated a significant effect on pain relief and physical function compared to the control groups. However, no significant improvement was found in the quality of life of patients treated with *Tui Na* compared to the control group. The safety profile appears to be favourable for *Tui Na*, as only six of the 15 studies reported adverse events, none of which were considered serious. Thus, the study suggests that the application of *Tui Na* can be an effective and safe strategy in the treatment of non-specific chronic low back pain, both for pain relief and for the improvement of physical function.

In cupping therapy, the common objective is to promote the extraction of toxic substances from the body through the production of negative pressure inside a cupping glass or a similar hollow object^{27,28}. In particular, wet/blood/bleeding cupping therapy is a therapeutic process that involves the initiation of superficial bleeding from small vessels or their branches, mainly in the skin and muscles, to decrease congestion in the area where the cups are applied and release accumulated toxic matter near the skin²⁹⁻³¹.

Chaoju *et al.*¹⁶ investigated the effectiveness and safety of bleeding cupping therapy in the treatment of non-specific low back pain. The study included 13 randomised clinical trials, with a total of 1088 participants. In pain relief, the technique was shown to be superior to other treatments in reducing pain, as measured by VAS. In addition, the results indicated that the technique was more effective than the control groups in improving physical function and reducing patient disability, as evaluated by the ODI. Other treatments included (for example) acupuncture, non-steroidal anti-inflammatories, manual therapy, and traditional cupping therapy. Regarding safety, the authors state that most of the included studies (7) did not report any adverse events. Only one study mentioned the occurrence of mild syncope in 7% of participants, but all recovered after a short period of rest. Concluding, it is suggested that bleeding cupping therapy is a safe and relatively effective therapy to relieve pain and improve physical function in patients with non-specific low back pain.

These results are in favour of the conclusions previously referred to in this work regarding the study by Deng *et al.*¹⁴, concerning the effectiveness of cupping therapy for the treatment of low back pain.

In the application of *Gua Sha*, the therapist uses a smooth-edged instrument to repeatedly scrape or rub acupuncture points, meridians, and other parts of the human body to produce transient petechiae and ecchymoses under the skin^{32,33}. This technique was investigated by Wang *et al.*¹⁷, who evaluated the effectiveness of *Gua Sha* in the treatment of chronic low back pain. The study included 10 randomised clinical trials with 627 participants.

In this study, the authors observed a statistically significant effect in pain reduction, with more than one session being necessary to feel relevant benefits. The study also revealed a significant improvement in lumbar function and a reduction in disability in patients who received *Gua Sha*. A subgroup analysis showed that *Gua Sha* had a promising effect on pain reduction and improvement of lumbar function one and three months after the end of treatment, respectively. Only one study reported adverse effects, none of which was considered serious. Therefore, it was possible to conclude that this technique can have a therapeutic effect for chronic low back pain, particularly in reducing pain and improving lumbar function.

3.3. Qigong and Taichi

Qigong consists of respiratory techniques combined with static or dynamic exercises and meditative processes with the aim of achieving a concrete therapeutic goal³⁴.

To evaluate the effects of *Qigong* on patients with non-specific chronic low back pain, Yu *et al.*¹⁸ developed a study that included and analysed 16 randomised clinical trials with 1175 participants. The authors observed that the practice of *Qigong* demonstrated a significant improvement in the degree of disability of patients compared to the control group, with a considerable effect size. Regarding pain intensity, the results for pain relief were more ambiguous. The study suggests that the practice of *Qigong* did not have a significant effect on pain improvement. Interestingly, short-term interventions showed superior effectiveness in pain scores when compared to long-term ones. Thus, the study was able to conclude that the practice of *Qigong* can be effective in improving disability in patients with non-specific chronic low back pain, but has a limited effect on pain relief.

In turn, Taichi (Tai Chi, Taichichuan or Taijiquan) can be defined as a system of gentle and slow exercises that promote mental awareness and physical health through the correction of *Qi* imbalances in the body³⁵.

Kang *et al.*¹⁹ studied the effectiveness of Taichi in the treatment of chronic low back pain. The study by these authors analysed 10 randomised clinical trials, with 886 participants in total. The results of this study suggest that Taichi can have a significant effect on the relief of chronic pain, with an effect size considered large and statistically significant. In addition, Taichi seems to have a large and significant impact on the reduction of physical disability associated with low back pain. However, it is also demonstrated that these techniques can improve the quality of life of patients, both physically and mentally.

Interestingly, the authors analysed some factors that could influence the results; however, the analyses found no significant differences in effectiveness between the different approaches of Taichi (alone or as a complementary therapy), between different styles (Chen and Yang) or relative to the duration of treatment (more than 30 sessions or less). Only the effectiveness of Taichi practised in water could not be proven. Moreover, according to this study, the incidence of adverse reactions was low. Due to the encouraging potential of the results, the study concluded that Taichi has an important effect on the relief of chronic low back pain, improving pain, disability, and quality of life.

4. Limitations

The results presented in the systematic reviews and meta-analyses on Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques for low back pain, although promising, should be interpreted with caution. A careful analysis of the studies, carried out by the authors of these reviews, reveals a series of methodological limitations that affect the strength of the evidence. The great diversity of participants, treatments (types and duration), acupuncture points used, and control groups (placebo or other therapies) introduces a high heterogeneity. This variability makes it difficult to make direct comparisons between studies and to consolidate robust conclusions.

In addition, many of the studies are of low to moderate methodological quality. Factors such as the absence of "blinding" (particularly of the therapist and the patient) and the lack of details on the random allocation of participants (selection bias) raise questions about the validity of the results. In addition, the limited number of studies and the small sample sizes in some of them reduce the statistical power, which means that it is more difficult to detect a real treatment effect, even if it exists.

Thus, although the findings suggest that Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques in general are effective in various aspects associated with low back pain, it is crucial to recognise that a high-quality evidence base does not yet support this effectiveness. Therefore, the final recommendation of almost all the studies included is that there is a need for more multicenter, large-scale, and rigorously designed randomised clinical trials to strengthen the clinical evidence and validate the findings.

5. Conclusions

The literature analysis carried out in this study suggests that Traditional Chinese Medicine offers a promising and effective approach to low back pain, in its acute and chronic, as well as specific and non-specific aspects. Evidence from high-quality studies, such as systematic reviews with meta-analyses, suggests that several Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques are superior to conventional and placebo approaches, particularly in reducing pain and improving physical function.

Acupuncture and electroacupuncture showed consistent results in pain relief and function improvement in different types of low back pain. Manual techniques such as *Tui Na* and *Gua Sha* also revealed positive effects on pain and function, with a favourable safety profile. In turn, cupping therapy with bleeding also stood out as an effective option for the reduction of pain and disability. Finally, movement practices such as *Qigong* and Taichi were shown to be beneficial for improving physical function and quality of life, although their effects on pain relief may be limited in some cases.

Despite the encouraging results, it is crucial to recognise that the evidence, in general, is of low/moderate quality. The limitations of the studies included in these meta-analyses require that the conclusions be interpreted with caution. Therefore, future studies, with greater methodological rigour and more robust samples are essential to solidify Traditional Chinese Medicine as a first-line intervention in the treatment of low back pain.

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